

Using Collective Intelligence to Detect Pragmatic Ambiguities

Alessio Ferrari, Stefania Gnesi
ISTI-CNR
Pisa, Italy
Email: {firstname.lastname}@isti.cnr.it

Abstract—This paper presents a novel approach for pragmatic ambiguity detection in natural language (NL) requirements specifications defined for a specific application domain.

Starting from a requirements specification, we use a Web-search engine to retrieve a set of documents focused on the same domain of the specification. From these domain-related documents, we extract different knowledge graphs, which are employed to analyse each requirement sentence looking for potential ambiguities. To this end, an algorithm has been developed that takes the concepts expressed in the sentence and searches for corresponding “concept paths” within each graph. The paths resulting from the traversal of each graph are compared and, if their overall similarity score is lower than a given threshold, the requirements specification sentence is considered ambiguous from the pragmatic point of view.

A proof of concept is given throughout the paper to illustrate the soundness of the proposed strategy.

Index Terms—requirements/specifications analysis; natural language; ambiguity detection; pragmatic ambiguity;

I. INTRODUCTION

In a structured software development process, technical requirements specifications are the primary landmark of any development activity, from preliminary design to final system validation. Along the process, different stakeholders with diverse skills are supposed to cope with the requirements, and since natural language (NL) is the most largely understood communication code, the specifications are typically expressed as NL documents.

Nevertheless, the feature of universality of NL hides a relevant problem: human language is inherently ambiguous, and so are the requirements sentences written in such a language. An ambiguous specification might lead to the development of a system that is not compliant with the expectations of the customer. It is therefore important to minimize ambiguities to avoid costly reworks on the product after its implementation.

Strategies and tools have been developed to deal with this problem [1]–[11]. The majority of the approaches are based on the identification of typical terms and constructions that have been recognized as frequent sources of ambiguous interpretation in practice [1]–[3], [6], [7], [11]. For example, Neumann [1] has stressed the ambiguity residing in the misplaced usage of the term “only”, while Berry and Kamsties [2] have pointed out dangerous usages of plurals and of the term “all”. A complete summary with examples of typical ambiguous expressions, together with the approaches to detect and avoid them, is given in the Ambiguity Handbook [3].

Besides some preliminary studies (see, e.g., [4], [5]), the usage of language understanding techniques for the detection of requirements ambiguities is still limited and, above all, suspiciously perceived by the requirements engineering community [12]. The most relevant arguments against the adoption of such techniques are based on an early paper of Ryan [12]. Here, the author correctly states that full automatic language understanding is unpracticable. Therefore, any NL processing approach aiming to replace the thinking requirement analyst is not desirable. Indeed, this apparently comfortable delegation might lead the analyst to rely on a defective tool and oversee serious omissions and errors. Hence, clerical tools that detect all the occurrences of problematic terms are preferred to programs that investigate the semantics of sentences.

We argue that these arguments are sound when talking about ambiguities residing in single terms, or related to the mutual relationships of terms belonging to the same sentence. However, a closer examination is required if we consider the so-called *pragmatic ambiguities* [3]. Such ambiguities derive from the *context* surrounding a requirement. The context includes the neighbouring requirements, the overall document and the knowledge of the person who reads the requirement. Part of the pragmatic ambiguities can be addressed at lexical or syntactic level (see, e.g., [11]). Nevertheless, given the large amount of contextual elements that participate to the generation - and *resolution* - of such ambiguities, rule-based clerical tools can hardly deal with the vast majority of them.

In this paper we present an approach for the detection of pragmatic ambiguities that takes into account the context of the specification. In particular, the method models the domain knowledge that is required for the interpretation of the requirements. To this end, a set of knowledge graphs is extracted from domain-related documents retrieved through Web-search engines. Moreover, the strategy considers also the relationships among requirements by mimicking the change in the domain knowledge that is experienced when reading neighbouring requirements. A running example is given throughout the paper as a proof of concept of the method.

The paper is structured as follows. In Sect. II, the rationale of the approach is presented. Sect. III illustrates the strategy adopted to model the domain knowledge. Sect. IV describes the algorithm used to detect ambiguities. Sect. V evaluates the time complexity of the method. Sect. VI summarizes the related work, and Sect. VII draws the final remarks.

II. RATIONALE

In a broad sense, ambiguity in a requirements specification resides in the possibility that different developers would give different interpretations to the same specification [13]. Ambiguity in NL requirements are normally classified into four main categories [3]: *lexical* (i.e., the terms used have several meanings), *syntactic* (i.e., the requirement sentence has more than one syntax tree, each one with a different meaning), *semantic* (i.e., the predicate logic expression equivalent to the sentence has more than one interpretation) and *pragmatic* (i.e., the meaning of the sentence depends on the *context* in which it is used).

In this paper, we focus on this last class of context-dependent ambiguities¹. The term *context* is used here as a general concept, which includes different levels: (1) those requirements immediately preceding and following the current one, (2) the other requirements placed in other sections of the document, (3) the *domain knowledge* of the developer reading the requirement, and (4) his so-called *common sense knowledge*, since the interpretation of a requirement might be based on concepts which are well known regardless of the domain experience of the developer. Pragmatic ambiguities at each context level might - or might not - be resolved at other context levels.

A. Pragmatic Ambiguity Example

In order to highlight the different context levels and their role in resolving pragmatic ambiguities, we consider a fragment of a sample requirements specification. The specification concerns an on-line bookstore that implements a *recommender system* to discover new books. Such a system is supposed to recommend books that the user might like, according to the book item currently selected by the user. Imagine that the readers of the following fragment are two different developers, with a background on recommender systems:

- 1) If the title of a book is entered by the user, then the system shall display the books having a title that matches the one entered by the user
- 2) If a book is purchased by the user, then the system shall add the book to the user preferences
- 3) If a book is selected by the user, then the system shall display similar books
- 4) The system shall display similar books on the bottom of the page
- 5) The system shall display similar books based on the user preferences of other users who purchased the same book during previous sessions
- 6) The system shall display similar books based on the topic of the book selected by the user

In this apparently simple example, one can identify several possible pragmatic ambiguities.

¹In this paper, we do not consider the case of *referential ambiguities* [3], which are normally classified as boundary cases between semantic and pragmatic ambiguities

R_4 speaks about the concept of *similar books*, which is not defined yet. Therefore, the expression might be considered ambiguous. However, R_5 and R_6 clarifies the parameters that make a book similar to another: its topic, and the preferences issued by other users. The interpretation of R_4 is therefore not ambiguous, since its ambiguity is resolved by the requirements following it.

R_4 also speaks about the concept of *page*: this concept does not appear in the presented fragment, but it might reasonably occur in other requirements of the document, for example those concerning the GUI of the system. In such a case, there is no ambiguity in R_4 . Otherwise, the requirement might be considered ambiguous in the context of the document, since there is not enough information to understand what is a *page*.

However, different developers might correctly interpret the requirement since the concept of *page* for an on-line system is well known. In such a case, the requirement is resolved in the context of the domain knowledge of the developers.

A similar case is R_5 , and the concept of *session* there cited. We assume that this concept does not appear in the rest of the document, and that it is not a common term for recommender systems practitioners. Given such assumptions, the developers would probably give their interpretation to the concept according to previously acquired knowledge in other domains, such as, e.g., communication protocols. In such a domain, a session can be referred to an HTTP session, or to a TCP session, depending on the protocol layer considered [14].

In common implementations, a TCP session is equivalent to a single request/response sequence at the application layer. HTTP sessions have a higher level of granularity, since a single HTTP session corresponds to several TCP sessions. The first developer might have a natural bias toward the interpretation of the term as TCP session, while the second one might automatically choose the HTTP session interpretation, without knowing the existence of the other possible sense. Therefore, R_5 is ambiguous since, given the same requirement, two developers can associate different senses to it, and possibly derive different implementations with diverse behaviour.

The rather common phenomenon exemplified is known as *unconscious disambiguation* [3]: people automatically give an interpretation to an expression, without considering that they are actually resolving an inherent ambiguity of the language.

Besides the peculiarity of the word “session”, chosen on purpose for our example, we believe that a high degree of pragmatic ambiguity in an expression - being it a single term, a phrase or a sentence - is associated with the following indicators: (1) the expression does not frequently occur in the requirement document; (2) the expression is not common in the given domain; (3) the expression is not associated with information that an ordinary person is supposed to know.

In our example, if the generic term “visit” would have been used in place of the more technical “session”, the ambiguity would probably be resolved at the common sense knowledge level. Besides, also substituting R_5 with the sentence “*The system shall display similar books based on collaborative filtering*” would have solved the ambiguity. The concept of

collaborative filtering is common in the recommender system domain, and its interpretation by practitioners would reasonably be the same.

B. Method Overview

The phenomenon known as unconscious disambiguation strongly depends on the background knowledge of each developer, both in terms of domain and common sense knowledge. Since no human knowledge-base is equal to another, the interpretation of a requirement by two subjects will always be different. However, if the interpretations are close enough to each other, we might expect the two subjects to use the requirements to build systems with an equivalent behaviour. Such a goal is actually the main objective to define unambiguous requirements specifications.

According to this intuition, we devise a method to detect pragmatic ambiguities, which is built in analogy with the example of the two developers. Following this metaphore, we build a set of n artificial subjects having a domain knowledge taken from domain-related documents retrieved through Web search engines. Fed with different documents belonging to the same domain, the algorithm creates a different knowledge-base relational graph for each artificial subject. This diversity in the graphs reflects the different background knowledge of the developers.

Once the n graphs are built according to the Web pages content, the requirements document is considered. The concepts expressed in each sentence are sequentially searched through the graphs. Navigating the knowledge-base according to the concepts expressed in the sentence can be regarded as the process of interpretation performed by one of our artificial subjects.

After each sentence search, we compare the sub-graphs that are activated during the traversal. If their similarity is lower than a given threshold, the requirement sentence is considered ambiguous, otherwise the sentence is reported as not ambiguous.

The power of the proposed method resides in the search algorithm adopted, which is built upon a generic procedure to compute the least-cost path in a graph. For each sentence that is evaluated, our algorithm leaves a trace in the graph: if the sentence embeds new concepts, these are added to the knowledge-base; if previously existing concepts are traversed, their role is re-enforced. This solution reflects the ability of a subject of acquiring knowledge from the requirements and use this information to understand the subsequent requirements. As previously observed, the understanding of a requirements depends on the neighbouring requirements and on the overall document.

III. DOMAIN KNOWLEDGE GRAPH CONSTRUCTION

Ontologies are the most commonly used tool to represent domain-related and common sense knowledge. An ontology is defined as an explicit representation of a conceptualization [15]. Well known general ontologies are WordNet [16], where concepts are associated to synsets (i.e., groups of

synonyms), and Cyc [17], where concepts are expressed in the form of relational rules. Interesting approaches exist, which allow the automatic extraction of ontologies from a set of documents retrieved through Web-search engines (see, e.g., [18]).

However, we found that these strategies are hardly applicable in our context. Indeed, they are mostly focused on creating stable ontologies by identifying those semantics aspects that are common to different people, while in our case we aim to emphasize the slightly different perception of a domain that two subjects may have.

In order to address this problem, we have defined an algorithm that incrementally builds a knowledge-base by processing the content of domain-specific documents.

The algorithm takes a set of documents as input, which are retrieved by querying a Web-search engine (e.g., Google, Google Scholar, Yahoo, Bing) with a set of representative terms of the domain.

The output of the algorithm is a *relational graph* that gives a navigable representation of the knowledge contained in this set of domain-specific documents retrieved through the Web. The nodes of the graph are the concepts contained in the documents, and the edges represent semantic connections among such concepts.

Such a relational graph is not an ontology in strict canonical terms. However, it has the desirable quality of being strongly dependent from the input documents chosen: given different documents on the same topic, the algorithm will derive different knowledge representations.

A. Domain Knowledge Representation

The preferred form to represent the domain knowledge is a directed weighted graph $G = \{V, E, w\}$. Each node $v \in V$ is associated to a concept. Each edge $e \in E \subseteq \{V \times V\}$ expresses a relationship among two concepts. The weighting function $w : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the inverse function of the semantic relatedness of two concepts. The more two concept are related, the lower the value returned by the weighting function.

a) *Nodes*: Each node is labeled with the morphological root of a relevant term contained in the document set. The relevant terms are those terms that are not part of the so-called *stop-words*, i.e., words which are common in English such as pronouns, prepositions, articles and conjunctions. We omit stop-words from our knowledge-base since they normally provide structure rather than content in a sentence. Indeed, we are here interested in associating the nodes to content-related concepts.

The use of morphological roots (also called *stems*) implies that terms such as “recommendation” and “recommender” are both represented by the same node “recommend”. In our case, the usage of morphological roots is based on the assumption that terms that share the same morphological root are normally related to the same concept, and therefore a single node can be used to represent them.

More formally, given the set of retrieved documents D , let $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ be the set of unique terms in D , i.e., the

vocabulary of terms, and let $\hat{T} = T \setminus \Omega$, where Ω is the set of English stop-words.

Moreover, let M be the set morphological roots, and let $\phi : T \rightarrow M$ be the stemming function [19] that maps each term into its morphological root.

The set V of nodes in the graph is labeled with the set of distinct morphological roots of those terms that are not stop-words. Formally, given the set of stems which are not stop-words $\bar{T} = \{\phi(t) \mid t \in \hat{T}\}$, we define a labeling function $\mathcal{L} : V \rightarrow \bar{T}$ that associates each node to a stem.

We argue that representing concepts as morphological roots of terms, instead of synsets as in Wordnet, is not too weak in our context. Indeed, the domains that are involved in the graph construction are technical domains, where a reduced vocabulary with a limited amount of synonyms is typically used. The same observation holds for the requirements documents that are analyzed with the support of the graph. In requirements specifications it is recommended to use always the same term to refer a concept. Furthermore, unnecessary synonymy can be effectively reduced through the approach that we proposed in a previous work [20].

b) Edges: Each directed edge in the graph is associated with the *co-occurrence* of two terms in the document set. We say that two terms co-occur when they appear along each other in a sentence. Co-occurrence normally indicates semantic proximity among concepts [21], and therefore we used it to represent concepts relationships. The nodes of our graph are not labeled with terms, but with stems. Hence, the concept of co-occurrence is in this case related to stems.

More formally, let the sentences $S \in D$ be represented as an ordered list of its stemmed terms excluding stopwords, i.e., $\bar{S} = (\phi(s) \mid s \in S, s \notin \omega)$. Two stems $\bar{t}_i, \bar{t}_j \in \bar{T}$ co-occur in D iff $\exists S \in D, \exists \bar{s}_h, \bar{s}_k \in \bar{S} : \bar{t}_i = \bar{s}_h, \bar{t}_j = \bar{s}_k, k = h + 1$.

Therefore, edges $e = (v_i, v_j) \in E$ in our graph are all those couples of nodes such that $\mathcal{L}(v_i), \mathcal{L}(v_j)$ co-occur in the document set.

The direction of each edge represents the order in which the stems connected by the edge can appear in a sentence of the document set.

For example, if we consider a sentence such as $S = \text{“Recommender systems typically produce a list of recommendations”}$, its stemmed version without stop-words is $\bar{S} = \{\text{‘recommend’}, \text{‘system’}, \text{‘typic’}, \text{‘produc’}, \text{‘list’}, \text{‘recommend’}\}$.

The co-occurrences contained in \bar{S} , and therefore the corresponding edges in the graph, are $\{(\text{‘recommend’}, \text{‘system’}), (\text{‘system’}, \text{‘typic’}), (\text{‘typic’}, \text{‘produc’}), (\text{‘produc’}, \text{‘list’}), (\text{‘list’}, \text{‘recommend’})\}$.

The direction of the edges is implicitly represented by the order of the terms, therefore an edge such as $(\text{‘recommend’}, \text{‘system’})$ is distinguished from $(\text{‘system’}, \text{‘recommend’})$.

c) Weighting Function: According to the definition of co-occurrence among stems given above, we define the co-occurrence frequency function $\chi : \bar{T} \times \bar{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, which associates to each couple of stems the number of their co-occurrences in the document set.

Each edge is labeled with a real positive number according to the weighting function w . Given an edge $e = (v_i, v_j) \in E$, the function is computed as $w(e) = 1/\chi(\mathcal{L}(v_i), \mathcal{L}(v_j))$. It is worth noting that the function is always defined, i.e., $\chi(\mathcal{L}(v_i), \mathcal{L}(v_j)) > 0$, since an edge exist in the graph if and only if the two stems that are connected by such edge co-occur in the original document set.

B. Graph Construction Algorithm

Given a domain, the set of documents D is retrieved through a Web-search engine by querying the engine with domain-representative terms.

An algorithm has been developed to build the relational graph associated to this set of domain-related documents. The algorithm, named BUILD-GRAPH, takes the document set D as input, together with the list of English stop-words Ω . The output of the algorithm is the relational graph in the form $G = \{V, E, W\}$, where W is a vector of weights. Each element of W is associated to an edge $e \in E$, and contains the weight of the edge according to the weighting function w .

The pseudo-code below reports the main procedure of the algorithm.

```

BUILD-GRAPH( $D, \Omega$ )
 $\bar{D}, V, E, W \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
 $\bar{D} \leftarrow \text{PRE-PROCESS}(D, \Omega)$ 
 $V \leftarrow \text{BUILD-NODES}(\bar{D})$ 
 $E, W \leftarrow \text{BUILD-EDGES}(\bar{D})$ 
return  $G \leftarrow \{V, E, W\}$ 

```

The algorithm is built upon three procedures, which are implemented as follows.

PRE-PROCESS: The procedure takes D and Ω as input, and implements the stop-words removal and the stemming tasks.

Each sentence belonging to D is processed by removing stop-words and by reducing each term to its stem through the stemming function ϕ . This function can be efficiently implemented through the widely used Porter stemming algorithm [22], which is able to compute the morphological root of a word in linear time with the number of letters of the word.

After this pre-processing, we have a set of sentences in the form of \bar{S} , according to the formalism of Sec. III-A. The pre-processed sentences are then grouped into a new set \bar{D} , which is manipulated by the subsequent procedures.

```

PRE-PROCESS( $D, \Omega$ )
 $\bar{D} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
for  $S \in D$ 
  do
     $\bar{S} \leftarrow (\phi(s) \mid s \in S, s \notin \Omega)$ 
     $\bar{D} \leftarrow \bar{D} \cup \bar{S}$ 
return  $\bar{D}$ 

```

BUILD-NODES: The procedure creates a node for each one of the unique stems found in each $\bar{S} \in \bar{D}$. To this end, the procedure simply scans the pre-processed sentences \bar{S} and, for each new stem found, a node identified by such a stem is added to the set of nodes V .

For the sake of simplicity, in the pseudo-code below we represent a node $v \in V$ labelled with \bar{s} directly with its label, hence we will not write $v(\bar{s})$ but simply \bar{s} .

```

BUILD-NODES( $\bar{D}$ )
   $V \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  for  $\bar{S} \in \bar{D}$ 
    do for  $\bar{s} \in \bar{S}$ 
      do if  $\bar{s} \notin V$ 
        then  $V \leftarrow V \cup \bar{s}$ 
  return  $V$ 

```

BUILD-EDGES: The procedure generates the edges E and a vector of weights W .

For each ordered couple of stems in each sentence $\bar{S} \in \bar{D}$, an edge is created in the graph.

In order to compute the final vector of weights W , a support vector X is used. Each element of X is associated to an edge to count the number of co-occurrences of the connected stems (i.e., the value of χ for the current edge).

When a new edge e is added, $X[e]$ is set to 1. If a co-occurrence is found for which an edge already exist, its $X[e]$ is increased by 1.

The final step of the procedure builds the vector of weights W by inverting each element of X .

```

BUILD-EDGES( $\bar{D}$ )
   $E, W, X \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  for  $\bar{S} \in \bar{D}$ 
    do for  $\bar{s}_h, \bar{s}_k \in \bar{S} : k = h + 1$ 
      do if  $(\bar{s}_h, \bar{s}_k) \notin E$ 
        then  $e \leftarrow (\bar{s}_h, \bar{s}_k)$ 
           $E \leftarrow E \cup e$ 
           $W[e], X[e] \leftarrow 1$ 
        else
           $X[e] \leftarrow X[e] + 1$ 
  for  $W[e] \in W$ 
    do  $W[e] \leftarrow 1/X[e]$ 
  return  $E, W$ 

```

The procedure increases $X[e]$ - and indirectly decrease the edge weight - whenever a co-occurrence is found among already connected stems. This solution reflects the need to reinforce the relationship among those concepts that frequently occur together. Indeed, we recall that lower values of weight for an edge imply higher relatedness among the connected concepts.

The final graph produced is composed by different connected components. These components can be regarded a partition of the knowledge into multiple contextual areas.

It is worth noting that, if we run the algorithm multiple times, each time feeding it with different domain-related documents sets as input, we expect to have different derived graphs as output. Indeed, the documents sets naturally contain different co-occurrences.

Nevertheless, we expect to see the same connections in the graphs for those concepts that are well-defined in the given domain: such concepts are likely to occur together in all the document sets. Furthermore, we expect these connections to be stronger (i.e., to have lower weight) if the connection

among such concepts is very frequent in the domain (i.e., the associated stems have a high-degree of co-occurrence).

C. Example

Considering the example of Sect. II-A, we query the Google Web-search engine and the Google Scholar engine with the domain-representative phrase “recommender system”. For the sake of our purposes, we simply consider the first document retrieved by Google as our first document set, and the first document retrieved by Google Scholar as our second document set. In particular, the retrieved documents are the Wikipedia article for the “Recommender System” entry, and a survey on the same topic written by Adomavicius and Tuzhilin [23].

We run the algorithm on both the documents to generate our relational graphs. The first graph contains 602 nodes, while the second one contains 909 nodes. We find that the two graphs have 305 nodes and 155 edges in common: these are concepts and concept relationships that we expect to be well-defined in the domain. As a confirmation to this statement, it is useful to consider an excerpt of the two graphs, centered in the “recommend” node.

Fig. 1. Fragment of the graph for the Wikipedia page

The nodes connected by edges that are common to both graphs are highlighted in grey.

We see that the edge connecting the stems “recommend” and “item” are common to both graphs. The same observation holds for the stems “content-bas” (stem of “content-based”) and “recommend”, which are intuitively well-established relationship in the recommender systems domain.

It is interesting to notice that the lowest weight for both graphs (0.04 for the Wikipedia page, and 0.02 for the Adomavicius and Tuzhilin paper) is achieved for the edge (“recommend”, “system”), which is a stemmed equivalent to the query submitted to the Web-search engines to perform the search. We argue that this is reasonably related to the Web-search engines ranking algorithm, which, besides other scores based on cross-links [24], naturally gives higher ranks to those pages with frequent occurrences of the queried terms.

Fig. 2. Fragment of the graph for the Adomavicius and Tuzhilin paper

In the context of our running example, it is also interesting to consider the second lowest-weighted edge. This is actually the pair (“collabor”, “filter”), weighted 0.08 for the first document and 0.07 for the second one. This strong connection suggests that the expression “collaborative filtering” is rather common in the considered domain, as already conjectured.

IV. AMBIGUITY DETECTION

When a human subject reads a sentence, she will activate concepts in her knowledge-base to perform interpretation of the sentence. The sentence is a sequential stream of words, and the concepts that are activated when reading it depend on the sequence of the terms. For example, reading the sequence of terms (“book”, “purchase”) will activate different concepts than those that are activated when reading (“book”, “title”). The activated concepts are those ones that are more related to the concepts sequentially expressed in the sentence. We argue that different pragmatic interpretations of a sentence by different subjects derive from the activation of different concepts in the knowledge-base of the subjects.

Back to our problem, we aim to detect pragmatic ambiguities in a requirements document. In our case, the knowledge-base of each subject is represented by a relational graph and the sentences that need an interpretation are those sentences contained in the requirements document. Activating related concepts in our graph implies traversing a minimum-weighted path from one concept in the sentence to the following concept in the sentence. Therefore, the interpretation of a requirement sentence can be regarded as the search of the *least-cost path* in the graph for each couple of neighbouring stems (i.e., concepts) in the input sentence.

Moreover, since the interpretation of a sentence does not depend solely on the previous knowledge, but also on the neighbouring requirements and on the overall document, the traversal of the graph has to affect the shape of the graph itself.

A. Least-cost Path Search for Sentence Interpretation

In order to give an algorithmic representation to these arguments, we developed an algorithm that is based on least-cost path search.

Given a directed weighed graph and two nodes, called source and goal, the least-cost path search problem is defined as the problem of searching the graph for a path with the lowest cost that connect the source node to the goal node. Roughly, a path in the graph is a sequence of nodes, each one connected by an edge. The weight of a path is the sum of the weights of the edges that connect the nodes of the path.

Several algorithms exist that are commonly used to compute the least-cost path between two given nodes. Among them, we recall the well-known Dijkstra, Bellman-Ford [25] and A^* [26] algorithms. In this work, we propose a generic approach where any of the mentioned procedures can be plugged to perform the search. Therefore, in the following we refer to the least-cost path search algorithm with a generic identifier, namely $\text{MIN-PATH}(x, y, V, E, W)$. Given a source node x , a goal node y and a weighted graph $G = \{V, E, W\}$, the search algorithm is required to return the least-weighted path between x and y . The proposed algorithm works as follows.

Given the sentences of our requirements document, these are pre-processed as previously performed on the domain-related documents. Each sentence in the requirement document is reduced to an ordered set of stems that are not stop-words, i.e., each requirement sentence R becomes \bar{R} , according to the previously introduced notation. Then, for each ordered couple (\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j) of stems such that $\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j \in \bar{R}$ and $j = i+1$, we perform a shortest-path search. We consider \bar{r}_i as the source, and \bar{r}_j as the goal. The final path P returned by the algorithm is the conjunction of the shortest-paths found for each (\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j) . In the literature a path like P is normally referred as a *connection subgraph* [27].

In order to integrate the knowledge contained in the requirements into the graph, and therefore influence the processing of the subsequent requirements, the algorithm performs three graph modification steps:

- 1) If a stem is found in \bar{R} that does not exist in the graph, a node is added to the graph, and such node is labeled with the new stem;
- 2) If a couple (\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j) is found without a corresponding edge in the graph, then the edge is created and its weight is initially set to 1;
- 3) For each edge that belong to one of the shortest-paths found, we reduce the edge weight according to the same policy adopted during the relational graph generation, i.e., for each $e \in P$ we increase the number of co-occurrences $X[e]$ by 1, and then we re-compute $W[e] \leftarrow 1/X[e]$.

The first two extension steps ensure that, if previously unknown concepts or concepts relationships are found during requirements reading, such items are added to the graph. The last step ensures that the traversal of concepts during requirements interpretation leaves a trace on the graph, by

reinforcing the edges that connect concepts included in the sentence. With these steps, we are able to represent also the additional knowledge given by the requirement document. Such additional knowledge, updated for each sentence processing, helps in the interpretation of those requirements that have not been evaluated yet.

The pseudo-code reported below illustrates the main procedure of our algorithm, named SENTENCE-PATH-SEARCH.

```

SENTENCE-PATH-SEARCH( $\bar{R}, V, E, W, X$ )
   $P \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
   $V \leftarrow \text{UPDATE-NODES}(\bar{R}, V)$ 
   $P \leftarrow \text{BUILD-MIN-PATH}(\bar{R}, V, E, W, X)$ 
  return  $P$ 

```

The procedure takes the pre-processed requirement sentence \bar{R} as input, together with the elements of the graph previously extracted through the BUILD-GRAPH procedure, namely V, E and W . The procedure uses also the previously computed vector X , which counts the number of co-occurrences.

The algorithm is built upon two procedures, which are implemented as follows.

UPDATE-NODES: The procedure implements the modification step 1 to add nodes to the graph if new stems are found in \bar{R} . The procedure scans the stems in $\bar{r}_i \in \bar{R}$ and, if there is no corresponding node in the existing graph, a node labeled with \bar{r}_i is added to the graph.

```

UPDATE-NODES( $\bar{R}, V$ )
  for  $\bar{r}_i \in \bar{R}$ 
    do if  $\bar{r}_i \notin V$ 
      then  $V \leftarrow V \cup \bar{r}_i$ 
  return  $V$ 

```

BUILD-MIN-PATH: The procedure returns a least-cost path P as a conjunction of sub-paths p in the graph. Each sub-path p is computed by the generic function MIN-PATH as the least-cost path that connect two co-occurring stems $\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j \in \bar{R} : j = i + 1$.

After searching for a least-cost path p , the procedure implements the modification steps 2 and 3. Indeed, if a path does not exist among two stems (i.e., $p = \emptyset$), an edge is added to connect them, and its weight is set to 1 (step 2). If a path p exists among the stems, then each edge $(p_h, p_k) \in p$ is reinforced by updating its weight (step 3).

```

BUILD-MIN-PATH( $\bar{R}, V, E, W, X$ )
   $P, p \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  for  $\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j \in \bar{R} : j = i + 1$ 
    do  $p \leftarrow \text{MIN-PATH}(\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j, V, E, W)$ 
    if  $p = \emptyset$ 
      then  $e \leftarrow (\bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j)$ 
       $E \leftarrow E \cup e$ 
       $X[e], W[e] \leftarrow 1$ 
       $p \leftarrow \bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j$ 
    else for  $p_h, p_k \in p : k = h + 1$ 
      do  $e \leftarrow (p_h, p_k)$ 
       $X[e] \leftarrow X[e] + 1$ 
       $W[e] \leftarrow 1/X[e]$ 
   $P \leftarrow P.p$ 
  return  $P$ 

```

The $P.p$ notation stands for the conjunction between the currently retrieved path P and the newly retrieved sub-path p . Roughly, the nodes in p are attached to P .

It is worth observing that there are two cases in which a new edge has to be added because a path does not exist among two stems: (1) at least one of the two stems \bar{r}_i, \bar{r}_j is a new node introduced during the UPDATE-NODES procedure; (2) the two stems connect different previously existing connected components.

The first case simply implies that the existing graph is extended with a new edge towards a node that is currently not connected to any other.

More interestingly, the second case implies that the existing graph has now a new connection among connected components that were previously separated. We recall that connected components can be regarded as different knowledge area of the same domain. Therefore, thanks to a single new edge, a whole set of concepts (i.e., a new knowledge area) is now reachable.

This solution mimics the common phenomenon that is normally experienced while reading a requirement document: when the same concept is found in sections that refer to different aspects of the system, it is natural to create a connection among the knowledge areas used to interpret the different system aspects. For example, when reading the term “page” in R4 of Sect. II-A, the analyst naturally links this term to the part of the requirements document where the GUI is described. Therefore, she activates that part of its knowledge-base related to GUI development in order to understand what is a “page”.

B. Interpretation Comparison

Given a requirement document, each requirement sentence is processed by the SENTENCE-PATH-SEARCH procedure. We assume that during the domain knowledge graph construction phase, a set of n graphs have been generated by running the algorithm on n documents sets. Therefore, the least-cost path search is performed n times for each requirement sentence, each time employing a different graph.

Since the knowledge-bases are different, the generated paths are likely to be different. However, we can perform a comparison among paths to evaluate their similarity. We state that, if the similarity value is lower than a threshold τ , the sentence may contain pragmatic ambiguities. Otherwise the sentence is not ambiguous, from the pragmatic point of view.

In order to compare the two paths, it is required to define a similarity metric. At this stage, we resorted to use an extension of the Jaccard similarity metric [28], defined as follows. Let P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n be the different paths and let $\bar{P}_1, \bar{P}_2, \dots, \bar{P}_n$ be the label of the nodes (i.e., the stems) contained in the paths. Moreover, let $\tilde{P}_1, \tilde{P}_2, \dots, \tilde{P}_n$ the stems in each path that have been added to the graphs by the UPDATE-NODES procedure.

The similarity of paths can be computed as:

$$\sigma_R(P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n) = \frac{|\bigcap_{i=1}^n (\bar{P}_i \setminus \tilde{P}_i)|}{|\bigcup_{i=1}^n (\bar{P}_i \setminus \tilde{P}_i)|}. \quad (1)$$

Somehow, this similarity metric measures the proportion of stems that the paths have in common, and it assumes that the greater is the number of shared stems, the higher is the chance of the paths to be similar.

It is worth noting that we do not include in the computation all those stems that have been added during the UPDATE-NODES procedure. These are all those new concepts that were not part of the graph. We exclude them from the computation in order to emphasize the role of those concepts that were already included in the domain knowledge before processing the current requirement. Such concepts actually participate to the interpretation of the requirement, while the newly added ones contribute to the interpretation of the subsequent requirements.

C. Example

In order to give a proof of concept of the approach, we now consider our sample requirements specification fragment, together with the two domain knowledge graphs derived from the Wikipedia page and from the Adomavicius and Tuzhilin paper. In the actual experiment, the fragment has been extended with other requirements to make the test more realistic.

We perform our evaluation through the sentence interpretation procedure using the Dijkstra algorithm as the MIN-PATH procedure. Then, we compare the retrieved paths through σ_R . The results are reported in Table I.

	R_1	R_2	R_3	R_4	R_5	R_6
σ_R	0.44	0.57	0.57	0.67	0.50	0.50

TABLE I
SIMILARITY METRIC FOR EACH SAMPLE REQUIREMENT

At this stage of the research we cannot devise a precise value for the threshold τ to discriminate ambiguous requirements from unambiguous ones. Nevertheless, we can notice that requirement R_1 , R_5 and R_6 have a sensibly lower value of σ_R , compared to the other requirements.

Let us consider for example the case of R_5 . The pre-processed version of such requirement is:

$\bar{R}_5 = \{\text{'system'}, \text{'shall'}, \text{'display'}, \text{'similar'}, \text{'book'}, \text{'base'}, \text{'user'}, \text{'prefer'}, \text{'user'}, \text{'purchas'}, \text{'book'}, \text{'previou'}, \text{'session'}\}$.

The paths $P_1(R_5)$, $P_2(R_5)$ derived through the different graphs for \bar{R}_5 are reported below. Bold style highlights the sub-path concepts that are traversed during the execution of the BUILD-MIN-PATH function, excluding the concepts in \bar{R}_5 used as source and goal for the search. Underlined text is used for those concepts that have been added during the BUILD-NODES procedure.

$P_1(R_5) = \{\text{'system'}, \text{'shall'}, \text{'display'}, \text{'similar'}, \text{'**user**'}, \text{'**may**'}, \text{'**avail**'}, \text{'book'}, \text{'**movi**'}, \text{'**user**'}, \text{'base'}, \text{'user'}, \text{'prefer'}, \text{'user'}, \text{'purchas'}, \text{'**onlin**'}, \text{'**store**'}, \text{'**will**'}, \text{'**play**'}, \text{'**music**'}, \text{'book'}, \text{'**movi**'}, \text{'**user**'}, \text{'previou'}, \text{'session'}\}$;

$P_2(R_5) = \{\text{'system'}, \text{'shall'}, \text{'display'}, \text{'similar'}, \text{'**user**'}, \text{'**recom-**'}, \text{'**mend**'}, \text{'book'}, \text{'**recommend**'}, \text{'base'}, \text{'user'}, \text{'prefer'}, \text{'user'}, \text{'**recom-**'}, \text{'**mend**'}, \text{'**product**'}, \text{'purchas'}, \text{'**store**'}, \text{'**user**'}, \text{'**recommend**'}, \text{'book'}, \text{'previou'}, \text{'session'}\}$.

One can notice that the only elements that the sub-paths have in common are the terms “store” and “user”. This low number of common elements in the sub-paths tells that the concepts that are activated during the interpretation of the sentence differ for the two graphs. Therefore, we argue that the sentence is liable to different interpretations.

Furthermore, we see that the only concept that has been added to both graphs during the BUILD-NODES procedure is the concept “session”. As already foreseen in Sect.II-A, this concept is not widely used in the domain and might lead to different interpretations. If we substitute the R_5 requirement with the sentence: “*The system shall display similar books based on collaborative filtering*”, as previously conjectured, we see that the value of σ_R increases to 0.6. In this case no concept is added to the graphs, since *collaborative filtering* is a common concept in the given domain.

A similar approach can be used to increase the value of σ_R for R_6 . In this case, one could substitute the requirement with the more technical sentence “*The system shall display similar books based on content-based filtering*”. In such a case the value of σ_R increases to 0.63 for the requirement.

The low value of σ_R of R_1 , which is a sentence that we intuitively consider not ambiguous, can be regarded as a false positive case due to the limited amount of documents used to build our graphs. Indeed, we found that concepts such as “title”, “enter” and others were new to both the graphs. The method is indeed not immune to false positive warnings, i.e., requirements improperly marked as ambiguous. However, false positive warnings are normally considered acceptable in a requirements analysis strategy for ambiguity detection [5]. As for any other tool for requirements analysis, the method does not aim to replace the analyst, but to give her support in highlighting possible ambiguities that she might oversee.

It is interesting to notice that, if we execute the algorithm multiple times on the same fragment, σ_R increases for some of the requirements. In particular, we observe that executing the procedure twice, the maximum increase of the σ_R value is achieved for R_3 , which changes from 0.57 to 0.72. This phenomenon is explained by the observation that processing subsequent requirements clarifies the preceding ones. In this context, σ_R for R_3 is affected by the processing of R_5 and R_6 , which clarify when books shall be considered similar. Therefore, we argue that the algorithm can be used to model also the explanation that subsequent requirements might give to preceding ones.

V. EVALUATION OF THE METHOD

A. Computational Complexity

We evaluate the worst-case time complexity of the method considering the two main tasks of the proposed strategy, namely *domain knowledge graph construction* and *ambiguity detection*.

We assume that the graph is stored in alfabetically ordered adjacency lists, where each node has an ordered list of which nodes it is adjacent to.

Assuming that a binary search strategy is employed, the time required to access a node or an edge is bounded by $O(\log(|V|))$, where $|V|$ is the number of nodes.

1) *Domain Knowledge Graph Construction*: The graph construction is performed by the BUILD-GRAPH procedure, and its time complexity is dominated by the BUILD-NODES procedure and by the BUILD-EDGES procedure. Both can be computed in $O(m \log(m))$, where m is the number of - possibly equal - words in the document set D .

This worst-case complexity is achieved with a document set D with terms that are all different from each other, are sorted in reverse alphabetical order and have no common stems.

We argue that this time complexity is acceptable, since the graphs are built only once for each application domain.

2) *Ambiguity Detection*: The ambiguity detection task can be regarded as two separate tasks, namely *least-cost path search* and *interpretation comparison*.

The least-cost path search is performed through the SENTENCE-PATH-SEARCH procedure, which is executed for each sentence in the requirement document. Its time complexity is dominated by the BUILD-MIN-PATH procedure.

With the reasonable assumption that the number of stemmed pairs in a requirement sentence is negligible with respect to the number of edges in the graph, the procedure is dominated by the complexity of the MIN-PATH algorithm employed. If, as in our example, a naive implementation of the Dijkstra algorithm is used, searching for a minimum path requires $O(|V|^2)$ [25].

The SENTENCE-PATH-SEARCH procedure for a single requirement sentence is repeated n times, where n is the number of relational graphs that have been defined. Therefore, the overall cost of the least-cost path search is $O(n|V_{max}|^2)$, where $|V_{max}|$ is the number of nodes of the graph with the highest number of nodes.

The interpretation comparison task is performed by computing the Jaccard metric for each path found in an execution of the SENTENCE-PATH-SEARCH procedure. If we assume that each stem in the path is not ordered, computing $\sigma_R(P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n)$ requires $O(|P_{max}|^n)$, where $|P_{max}|$ is the maximum length of a path. In the worst case $|P_{max}| = |V_{max}|$ (i.e., the whole graph is returned), therefore we have that the computation requires $O(|V_{max}|^n)$.

It is worth observing that, if more than two relational graphs are used, the interpretation comparison step dominates the least-cost-path search implemented through the Dijkstra algorithm. Indeed, in such a case we have $n > 2$, and therefore $O(n|V_{max}|^2) \subset O(|V_{max}|^n)$. Hence, given a requirement specification document D_R with $|D_R|$ sentences, the overall worst-case time complexity of the ambiguity detection task using n domain knowledge graphs is:

$$C = \begin{cases} O(|D_R||V_{max}|^2), & \text{if } n = 2. \\ O(|D_R||V_{max}|^n), & \text{if } n > 2. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

B. Scalability

We argue that, though the procedures required to implement the method have relevant time complexities, the approach

is scalable to real-size problems. The observations reported below give support to this statement.

Graphs Construction: The construction of the graphs is performed only once for a given domain. A company operating in a sector can use the same set of graphs for different projects, with considerable time savings after the first application;

Vocabulary Size: The vocabulary of a domain is limited. Therefore, $|V_{max}|$ is a manageable quantity that cannot increase indefinitely, and this makes the complexity of the method reasonably acceptable;

Small-world Property: For many of the real-world data problems, the relational graphs such as the one we are using have been found to have the so-called *small-world* property [29]. Such a property implies that they have small average distance among each pair of nodes. This phenomenon is witnessed for example by the well known social experiment concerning the six degrees of separation among two randomly selected people [30]. Another related work is reported in [31], where the typical number of links to reach one Web-page from another is found to be 19. We currently do not have any proof that the small world property found in these graphs also hold in our domain knowledge graphs. Nevertheless, the paths discovered in our experiment seem to confirm this conjecture. For the considered fragment, we have seen that each requirement stem is connected to another with a maximum distance of 5 nodes for the first graph, and 4 nodes for the second. Moreover, the average distance is around 1 node for both the graphs.

Balanced choice of n: In our example, we have seen that already with two graphs we are able to identify relevant pragmatic ambiguities. We argue that increasing the number of graphs n might give higher confidence on the ambiguities revealed. Intuitively, having more graphs is comparable to having a larger amount of requirements analysts discussing on the ambiguity of the same requirement. On the other hand, increasing n would also increase the time required for the execution of the algorithm. Hence, a proper balance between time-effectiveness and confidence on the ambiguities detected shall be devised when employing the method. For example, one could select $n > 2$ when the level of criticality of the requirements under exam is higher, and $n = 2$ otherwise;

Limited $|D_R|$: The number of sentences in a requirements specification document, i.e., the value of $|D_R|$, is normally limited. According to our previous experience, it is usually in the order of the hundreds also for industrial specifications [6].

VI. RELATED WORKS

Several studies have been conducted in the past to support the analysis of NL requirements specifications and limit their inherent ambiguity. A primary reference is the thorough work of Berry *et al.* [3]. Here, a taxonomy is provided to distinguish the different types of NL ambiguities, together with typical examples of problematic expressions. According to this study, our laboratory has developed QuARS [6], a tool that detects ambiguities according to keyword-based linguistic indicators. A similar approach is followed by ARM [7].

Other interesting tools, not solely focused on requirements disambiguation, are LOLITA [8] and Circe-Cico [9]. The first is a general purpose NL analysis framework that employ a large hierarchical semantic network as a knowledge base. Here, ambiguity detection is performed by integrating the text into the network to perform automatic interpretation. The tool has been employed also to generate object-oriented models. The second tool, Circe-Cico, allows the progressive transformation of NL requirements into formal models. Still bound to formal model generation are the notable works of Kof (see, e.g., [10]).

The only study where pragmatic ambiguities in requirements are explicitly addressed is the work of Gleich *et al.* [11]. However, in this paper pragmatic ambiguities are always resolved at syntactic or semantic level, while in our work we exploit contextual information.

From the methodological viewpoint, our approach is similar to the one of LOLITA. However, the proposed strategy differs from the generic approach of such tool since (1) we exploit domain-dependent knowledge, (2) we use multiple knowledge-bases automatically built from Web documents.

To the knowledge of the authors, the present work is the first attempt in the literature that aims to detect pragmatic ambiguities in requirements specifications by leveraging contextual information and domain-specific Web documents.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel approach for detecting pragmatic ambiguities in NL requirements specifications is presented. The approach addresses the problem of involving the *context* in the analysis of the requirements. The context is represented by the other requirements in the same documents, and by the domain knowledge typically required for the interpretation of the specification. At this stage, we did not model the common-sense knowledge, which is another relevant contextual aspect when talking about NL understanding. Nevertheless, we envision that this aspect can be included by connecting our method with an established ontology such as WordNet or Cyc. We are currently delving strategies to address this issue.

From the implementation point of view, an automatic tool based on the presented method shall consider to employ the Yahoo BOSS API, instead of Google, since the latter does not provide any interface anymore. Furthermore, PDF pre-processing shall be taken into account. Indeed, great part of the documents that embeds relevant domain knowledge are research papers, rarely available in plain text form.

Despite implementation-related issues and possible extensions, we argue that the proposed method is scalable to real-world-sized problems. We have shown that the time complexity of the approach is smoothed by the limited dimension of the actual vocabulary of the domain knowledge, and by the limited amount of sentences in a requirement document. An interesting evolution of the research is the assessment of the small-world property for domain knowledge graphs. If such a property would be confirmed by the practice, novel approaches for NL understanding could be devised based on this finding.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. G. Neumann, "Only his only grammarian can only say only what only he only means," *ACM SIGSOFT SE Notes*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 6, 1986.
- [2] D. M. Berry and E. Kamsties, "The syntactically dangerous all and plural in specifications," *IEEE Software*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 55–57, 2005.
- [3] D. M. Berry, E. Kamsties, and M. M. Krieger, "From contract drafting to software specification: Linguistic sources of ambiguity," 2003.
- [4] L. Mich and R. Garigliano, "Ambiguity measures in requirements engineering," in *Proc. of ICS'00, 16th IFIP WCC*, 2000, pp. 39–48.
- [5] N. Kiyavitskaya, N. Zeni, L. Mich, and D. M. Berry, "Requirements for tools for ambiguity identification and measurement in natural language requirements specifications," in *Proc. of WER'07*, 2007, pp. 197–206.
- [6] S. Gnesi, G. Lami, and G. Trentanni, "An automatic tool for the analysis of natural language requirements," *IJCSSE*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 53–62, 2005.
- [7] W. M. Wilson, L. H. Rosenberg, and L. E. Hyatt, "Automated analysis of requirement specifications," in *Proc. of ICSE'97*, 1997, pp. 161–171.
- [8] L. Mich, "NL-OOPS: from natural language to object oriented requirements using the natural language processing system LOLITA," *NLE*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 161–187, 1996.
- [9] V. Ambriola and V. Gervasi, "On the systematic analysis of natural language requirements with Circe," *ASE*, vol. 13, pp. 107–167, 2006.
- [10] L. Kof, "From requirements documents to system models: A tool for interactive semi-automatic translation," in *Proc. of RE'10*. IEEE Computer Society, 2010, pp. 391–392.
- [11] B. Gleich, O. Creighton, and L. Kof, "Ambiguity detection: Towards a tool explaining ambiguity sources," in *Proc. of REFSQ'10*, ser. LNCS, vol. 6182. Springer, 2010, pp. 218–232.
- [12] K. Ryan, "The role of natural language in requirements engineering," in *Proc. of ISRE'93*, 1993, pp. 240–242.
- [13] A. Davis, *Software Requirements: Objects, Functions and States*. Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [14] H. Bidgoli, *The Handbook of Computer Networks*. Wiley, 2007.
- [15] T. R. Gruber, "A translation approach to portable ontology specifications," *Knowledge Acquisition*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 199–221, 1993.
- [16] G. A. Miller, "Wordnet: A lexical database for english," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 39–41, 1995.
- [17] D. B. Lenat, "Cyc: A large-scale investment in knowledge infrastructure," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 38, no. 11, pp. 32–38, 1995.
- [18] P. Pantel and M. Pennacchiotti, "Automatically harvesting and ontologizing semantic relations," in *Ontology Learning and Population: Bridging the Gap between Text and Knowledge*, ser. FAIA. IOS Press, 2008, vol. 167, pp. 171–195.
- [19] J. B. Lovins, "Development of a stemming algorithm," *MTCL*, vol. 11, pp. 22–31, 1968.
- [20] A. Ferrari, S. Gnesi, and G. Tolomei, "A clustering-based approach for discovering flaws in requirements specifications," in *Proc. of SAC'12 (to appear)*, 2012.
- [21] P. D. Turney and P. Pantel, "From frequency to meaning: Vector space models of semantics," *J. Artif. Intell. Res.*, vol. 37, pp. 141–188, 2010.
- [22] M. F. Porter, "An Algorithm for Suffix Stripping," *Program*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 130–137, 1980.
- [23] G. Adomavicius and A. Tuzhilin, "Toward the next generation of recommender systems: A survey of the state-of-the-art and possible extensions," *IEEE Trans. KDE*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 734–749, 2005.
- [24] S. Brin and L. Page, "The anatomy of a large-scale hypertextual web search engine," *Comput. Netw. ISDN Syst.*, vol. 30, pp. 107–117, 1998.
- [25] T. H. Cormen, C. Stein, R. L. Rivest, and C. E. Leiserson, *Introduction to Algorithms*, 2nd ed. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, 2001.
- [26] P. Hart, N. Nilsson, and B. Raphael, "A Formal Basis for the Heuristic Determination of Minimum Cost Paths," *IEEE Trans. SSC*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 100–107, 1968.
- [27] C. Faloutsos, K. S. McCurley, and A. Tomkins, in *Proc. of KDD'04*, pp. 118–127.
- [28] P.-N. Tan, M. Steinbach, and V. Kumar, *Introduction to Data Mining*. Addison-Wesley, 2005.
- [29] D. J. Watts and S. H. Strogatz, "Collective dynamics of 'small-world' networks," *Nature*, vol. 393, no. 6684, pp. 440–442, 1998.
- [30] S. Milgram, "The small world problem," *Psychology Today*, vol. 2, pp. 60–67, 1967.
- [31] R. Albert, H. Jeong, and A. L. Barabasi, "The diameter of the world wide web," *Nature*, vol. 401, pp. 130–131, 1999.